

Supporting Information

DFT Functionals for Modeling of Polyethylene
Chains Cross-linked by Metal Atoms. DLPNO-
CCSD(T) Benchmark Calculations

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Figure S1 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals for non-crosslinked PEX...PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X in each chain, plotted separately. If not noted explicitly, functionals are supplemented by D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions expect of M06, M06L and M06-2X functionals which are not-supplemented by any D3 contribution.

Figure S2 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X (X = 3, 5, 7, 9) in each chain. If not noted explicitly, functionals are supplemented by D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions expect of M06, M06L and M06-2X functionals which are not-supplemented by any D3 contribution.

Figure S3 MAPE (%) of BEs 25 DFT functionals for non-crosslinked PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes with different number of carbon atoms X in each chain. If not noted explicitly, functionals are supplemented by D3(BJ)-ABC dispersion contributions except of M06, M06-L and M06-2X functionals which are not-supplemented by any D3 contribution.

Figure S4 Dependence of BEs CBS limit of PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) and crosslinked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. Dependences are plotted for two best performing DFT functionals CAM-B3LYP+D3(BJ)-ABC (A), ω B97X-D3 (B), and for PBE0+D3(BJ)-ABC (C).

A)

B)

C)

Figure S5 Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of PEX...PEX (X = 4, 5, 7 and 9) complexes and cross-linked PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Be, Mg, Zn, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. BEs were calculated using DLPNO-CCSD(T) method with QRO orbitals. Dependences are plotted for two basis sets def2-TZVPP (A), def2-QZVPP (B) and the CBS limit (C). BEs are calculated with respect to fragments 2PE4*.

A)

B)

C)

Table S1. Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of non-cross-linked PEX \cdots PEX (X = 4, 5, 7, 9) complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. BEs were calculated using DLPNO-CCSD(T) method with QRO orbitals for two basis sets def2-TZVPP, def2-QZVPP and CBS limit. All BEs at the CBS limit are extrapolated from def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets. BEs are calculated with respect to fragments 2PE4*.

PEX \cdots PEX	def2-TZVPP	def2-QZVPP	CBS
X = 4	-7.9	-9.3	-10.3
X = 5	-11.0	-12.6	-13.8
X = 7	-16.8	-19.1	-20.7
X = 9	-22.5	-25.1	-27.0

Table S2. Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. BEs were calculated using DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method for PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes and DLPNO-CCSD(T) method for PEX-M-PEX (M = Be, Mg, Zn; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes using QRO orbitals and def2-TZVPP basis set. BEs are calculated with respect to fragments PE3-M + PE3.

PEX-M-PEX	Li ^c	Be ^c	Mg ^c	Zn ^c	Ag ^c	Au ^c
X = 3	-36.6	-371.0	-242.5	-278.3	-65.1	-95.4
X = 5	-43.0	-380.6	-253.7	-287.5	-73.7	-103.2
X = 7	-50.9	-383.0	-255.6	-289.4	-78.7	-104.8
X = 9	-56.7	-386.5	-259.0	-293.0	-83.7	-109.1

^cComplexes PE3-Be-PE3, PE3-Mg-PE3 and PE3-Zn-PE3 are singlets, their fragments are doublets; PE3-Li-PE3, PE3-Ag-PE3, and PE3-Au-PE3 doublets, their PE3-M and PE3* fragments are singlets and doublets, respectively.

Table S3. Dependence of BEs (kJ/mol) of cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. BEs were calculated using DLPNO-CCSD(T1) method for PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes and DLPNO-CCSD(T) method for PEX-M-PEX (M = Be, Mg, Zn; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes using QRO orbitals and def2-QZVPP basis set. BEs are calculated with respect to fragments PE3-M + PE3.

PEX-M-PEX	Li ^c	Be ^c	Mg ^c	Zn ^c	Ag ^c	Au ^c
X = 3	-39.9	-384.1	-250.9	-290.1	-73.1	-104.8
X = 5	-46.5	-394.0	-262.8	-300.4	-82.9	-113.8
X = 7	-54.8	-396.4	-264.4	-302.2	-88.2	-115.5
X = 9	-61.4	-400.4	-268.1	-305.4	-93.9	-120.3

^cComplexes PE3-Be-PE3, PE3-Mg-PE3 and PE3-Zn-PE3 are singlets, their fragments are doublets; PE3-Li-PE3, PE3-Ag-PE3, and PE3-Au-PE3 doublets, their PE3-M and PE3* fragments are singlets and doublets, respectively.

Table S4. Dependence CBS limit BEs (kJ/mol) of cross-linked PEX-M-PEX complexes on the number of carbon atoms in the oligomer. DLPNO-CCSD(T1) was used for PEX-M-PEX (M = Li, Ag, Au; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes and DLPNO-CCSD(T) was used for PEX-M-PEX (M = Be, Mg, Zn; X = 3, 5, 7, 9) complexes. All BEs at the CBS limit are extrapolated from def2-TZVPP and def2-QZVPP basis sets data. For both basis set QRO orbitals were used.

PEX-M-PEX	Li ^c	Be ^c	Mg ^c	Zn ^c	Ag ^c	Au ^c
X = 3	-42.3	-393.6	-257.1	-298.7	-79.0	-111.6
X = 5	-49.1	-403.9	-269.4	-309.9	-89.7	-121.5
X = 7	-57.7	-406.2	-270.8	-311.4	-95.2	-123.3
X = 9	-64.8	-410.5	-274.7	-314.5	-101.3	-128.4

^cComplexes PE3-Be-PE3, PE3-Mg-PE3 and PE3-Zn-PE3 are singlets, their fragments are doublets; PE3-Li-PE3, PE3-Ag-PE3, and PE3-Au-PE3 doublets, their PE3-M and PE3* fragments are singlets and doublets, respectively.